

Thermodynamic mapping of a R744 simple cycle for HTHPs: application to a brewery process

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Abstract. High Temperature Heat Pumps (HTHPs) are a key technology toward industry decarbonization. Based on the variety of needs and boundaries, significant research efforts are underway to identify the best technical solutions and the most suitable refrigerants. Among natural refrigerants, which offer long-term sustainable options, carbon dioxide (CO₂) presents additional safety benefits. This paper conducts a thermodynamic analysis of a simple CO₂ cycle, exploring its application limits as HTHP working fluid. It presents a map of the maximum Coefficient of Performance (COP), along with its corresponding operating points as functions of source and sink inlet temperatures and sink temperature lift. The methodology incorporates pinch point analysis for the gas cooling process, enabling precise optimization of CO₂ thermodynamic cycles under varying conditions. The findings serve as preliminary design recommendations to discuss HTHP applicability. The outcomes of this study are applied to the heating processes of a small craft brewery, to quantify the impact of a HTHP as a substitution for gas burners and limiting electric heaters' contributions, while keeping simplicity in the system layout and complying with safety requirements for indoor installations.

Keywords: High Temperature Heat Pump, CO₂, Thermodynamic Analysis, Pinch Point, COP.

1 INTRODUCTION

High-temperature heat pumps are a key solution for reducing fossil fuel use and increasing renewable energy adoption in industry. Natural working fluids (NWFs) such as CO₂, NH₃, H₂O, air, and hydrocarbons can offer long-term sustainable solutions, once that most suitable applications are identified for the thermophysical properties of each of them. CO₂ stands out for its non-toxic, non-flammable nature, ODP of 0, GWP of 1, and excellent heating and cooling performance, thanks to its properties [1,2]. Operating in a transcritical cycle above 73.8 bar and 31.18°C, CO₂ achieves optimal performance through independent control of high-side pressure and temperature [1]. Transcritical CO₂ heat pump performance

depends on heat rejection pressure and the pinch point, where fluid temperature differences are minimal [2, 3]. Assuming a constant CO₂ exit temperature based on heat rejection fluid temperature introduces errors, especially at low temperatures [4, 5].

Within the framework of iNEST [6] (Interconnected Nord-Est Innovation Ecosystem), this work aims at identifying opportunities to reduce emissions in thermal industrial processes by implementing HTHP in place of fossil fuel burners and promoting waste heat recovery. Additionally, the use of NWFs as refrigerants in heat pumps and refrigeration systems represents a long-term sustainable option toward a net-zero scenario. The expected results focus on the best NWF HTHP options in the range of 90-150°C for hot water or steam.

The specific objective of this paper is to simulate the transcritical or supercritical CO₂ heat pump thermodynamic cycle with an internal heat exchanger, based on pinch-point analysis for the gas cooling process. Then, the goal is to implement an optimization function that maximizes COP, explores the design space, maps thermodynamic cycles, and identifies optimal configurations under given constraints to highlight the optimal performances and operation point.

These maps are then used to assess the impact, in terms of energy and emissions, of a CO₂ HTHP as substitute of a gas burner in the heating processes of a small craft brewery.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Thermodynamic Cycle Definition

A simple thermodynamic cycle with a regenerative heat exchanger was considered in this study, as shown in Fig. 1. Such a cycle can be a reasonable and economically sustainable option for small applications, where the investment cost and system complexity represent a barrier to the introduction of these new systems. The thermal sink of the cycle will be defined based on the secondary fluid's inlet and outlet temperatures, referring to the process the HTHP is serving.

2.2 Input Parameters and Assumptions

Thermodynamic properties of CO₂ were determined using REFPROP [7]. The following assumptions were made for calculating the cycle:

- Minimum temperature difference in the gas cooler and in the evaporator: $dT = 3\text{K}$;
- Compressor overall efficiency: estimated using manufacturer's data [8];
- Compressor maximum discharge temperature: 150°C;
- Compressor maximum discharge pressure: 150 bar;
- Internal Heat Exchanger (IHX) efficiency: 0.8;
- Ideal constant temperature thermal source;
- Constant property secondary fluid in the thermal sink.

Fig. 1. The HTHP schematic: a) system and main components; b) thermodynamic cycle.

2.3 Numerical model

The script solving the thermodynamic cycle shown in Fig. 1, as well as all the other scripts in this work have been developed in MATLAB [9].

The pressures (p_1 and p_2) and the sink temperatures (T_{Sink}^i and T_{Sink}^o) are the inputs of the numerical scheme, that is iterative to solve the internal feedback given by the internal heat exchanger. Point 1 (Fig. 1), which represents the output of the evaporation process, is determined based on the evaporation pressure, and the maximum obtainable temperature according to the approach (dT) that is $T_{Source} - dT$. It is the only point that doesn't require an update during the iterative procedure. Point 1_{ihx} is obtained given the heat exchanger efficiency and the temperature T_3 , if T_3 is higher than T_1 . Otherwise, the internal heat exchanger is ignored. The isentropic efficiency of the compressor and the high-pressure are then used to obtain point 2.

As the gas cooling process implies a nonlinear relationship between temperature and enthalpy decrease on the CO₂ side of the exchanger, the heat exchange in the gas cooler is not univocally defined by the temperature T_2 , the sink inlet temperature (T_{Sink}^i), and the minimum distance between the profiles (dT). In fact, different outlet temperatures can be obtained by changing the position (temperature) of the pinch point. In this study, the pinch point temperature is solved by a dedicated subfunction so to obtain the desired temperature at the process outlet (T_{Sink}^o). Once the pinch point temperature (T_{pp}) is assessed, given T_{Sink}^i and T_{Sink}^o , Point 3 can be determined. Point 3_{ihx} is obtained by enforcing the energy balance of the internal heat exchange, while an isenthalpic transformation to the low pressure is assumed to obtain Point 4.

The cycle is initialized by assuming $T_3 = T_{Source} + dT$ and is updated at each iteration until it converges where the change between iterations is within the prescribed tolerance.

The performance of the cycle is quantified using the Coefficient of Performance (COP):

$$COP = \frac{h_2 - h_3}{h_2 - h_{1_{ihx}}} \quad (1)$$

2.4 Mapping Design Space

HTHP can be applied on a wide range of different processes. On the source side, some installations can rely on medium temperature waste heat or use the ambient as source. The thermal sink side, that reflects the needs of each specific application, can differ in terms of target temperature (T_{Sink}^o) and temperature lift ($T_{Sink}^o - T_{Sink}^{io}$).

To cover a representative portion of the actual applications, in this study, three different source temperatures have been considered (10, 20 and 30°C) and all the possible combinations of T_{Sink}^i and T_{Sink}^o according to the following ranges:

- T_{Sink}^i : 10...80 °C (discretized using a 1 K step)
- T_{Sink}^o : 70...120 °C (discretized using a 1 K step)

For each set of boundaries composed by T_{Source} , T_{Sink}^i , and T_{Sink}^o a full grid of low and high pressures (P_1 and P_2) values are considered in the following ranges:

- P_1 : evaporation temperature range was parametrized after the source temperature. The highest possible evaporation temperature was set to $T_{Source} - dT$. This temperature was then decreased in steps of 1.5 K down to $T_{Source} - dT - 9$ K
- P_2 : 85 ... 150 bar (discretized using 0.5 bar step)

2.5 Optimization Framework

Each triple (T_{Source} , T_{Sink}^i , T_{Sink}^o) can be satisfied by an entire set of thermodynamic cycles, characterized by the triple (p_1 , p_2 , T_{pp}). These overlaps, with varying pressures and pinch points temperatures but identical boundaries, grant the degrees of freedom for an optimization problem:

$$\underset{x=(P_1, P_2, T_{pp})}{argmax} COP(x) \quad \text{for given application } (T_{Source}, T_{Sink}^i, T_{Sink}^o) \quad (2)$$

The optimization problem was then solved for each triple (T_{Source} , T_{Sink}^i , T_{Sink}^o) using golden section search algorithm [9] while the function $COP(x)$ was approximated interpolating the data collected from the design space sampling described in section 2.4.

3 RESULTS

The results of the optimization are reported in the following figures: Fig. 2 reports colored maps of maximum COP in T_{Sink}^i ; T_{Sink}^o maps, for different T_{Source} while Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 present the operating conditions of the cycle corresponding to the maximum COP. Whereas in Fig. 3 the high pressure p_2 is presented, in Fig. 4 the low pressure p_1 is presented by plotting the offset of the evaporation temperature with respect to the maximum possible ($T_{Source} - dT$).

Fig. 2. Colored maps of maximum COP for different T_{Source} : a) 10°C; b) 20°C; c) 30°C.

Fig. 3. Colored maps of optimum p_2 for different T_{Source} : a) 10°C; b) 20°C; c) 30°C.

Fig. 4. Optimum evaporation temperature offset from highest allowed evaporation temperature maps for different T_{Source} : a) 10°C; b) 20°C; c) 30°C.

As expected, the heat pump cycle performs very well when working when the secondary fluid entering the gas cooler (T_{Sink}^i) is cold. This allows the cycle to take full advantage of the glide in CO₂ temperature during the heat transfer process. The cycle presents satisfactory performance (COP > 3) for all the cases when T_{Sink}^i is lower than 40°C. Above this limit, the COP becomes almost independent on T_{Sink}^o (vertical iso-lines) and monotonically decreases.

For relatively low T_{Sink}^i (<40°C), optimal p_2 increases with T_{Sink}^o to push the cycle toward higher allowed T_2 , to match the temperature profile as much as possible. For T_{Sink}^i higher than 40°C, p_2 increase quickly with T_{Sink}^i whatever the T_{Sink}^o is reaching the maximum allowed pressure for $T_{Sink}^i \approx 60$ °C. In this case, optimal p_2 is driven by T_{Sink}^i : p_2 increases to maintain the point 3 of the cycle on the left of the critical point, compensating the extra compressor work with higher enthalpy exchange.

The optimal evaporation temperature (Fig. 4) is, as expected, the highest possible for T_{Source} equal to 10 and 20 °C. However, for $T_{Source} = 30$ °C, the optimal evaporation temperature is between 3 and 7°C lower than the maximum one as per imposed temperature difference (Section 2.2). Being close to the critical point, lowering the evaporation temperature allows to move point 2 to higher enthalpy; in such a way the larger heating effect positively compensated the higher compression work. This is combined with the optimization of P_2 described above that controls the position of Point 3.

An interesting insight from this analysis shows that, when the system reaches the maximum pressure, the only way to further increase the pressure ratio (and avoid the enthalpy difference between point 2 and 3 to be excessively small) is by stepping down the evaporation. The highest gradients in the optimal evaporation pressure maps, in fact, correspond to the area where the high pressure is close to the maximum value (150 bar).

4 BREWERY

The heat demand in the temperature range 60 – 100°C covers a non-negligible share of the total demand and is specifically relevant in the food industry [11]. The performance maps presented above can be used as a tool to assess the impact of a CO₂ HTHP as a substitution of burners or electrical heating. While benefits can be obtained by the simple replacement of the old equipment, others can be obtained by leveraging the specific features of CO₂ HTHP by adapting the process itself to the new unit. In this paper, a small artisanal brewery in northern Italy, which operates with intermittent production and has two 500-liter fermentation tanks, has been used as test case to present this. The brewery is located in a multifunctional building with limited access to external spaces, meaning the equipment must be installed within the working area. This constraint makes it difficult to implement a hydrocarbon or ammonia heat pump.

4.1 Process & Baseline technology

In this brewery process case study, we will focus on only the initial thermal processes where the control over temperature and time is very important. First, 1400 kg of water is heated from 10°C to 80°C. Most of this water is used in the cleaning cycle, while a small portion is used in mashing which refers to the process of mixing ingredients of beer with water. This mixture is heated to specific temperatures to activate enzymes that convert starches into fermentable sugars. Mashing is a key step in brewing that forms the basis for producing wort (the liquid extracted for fermentation) [12]. During the mashing phase, 450 kg of heated water is combined with 150 kg cold ingredients, which lowers the temperature of the mixture to 60°C. The mixture is then gradually heated from 60°C to 80°C at a rate of 1 K/min to ensure control thermal adjustment. After reaching 80°C, the wort is further heated to 100°C. Finally, during the boiling phase, the wort is evaporated to remove approximately 10% of its mass over 75 minutes. This evaporation step is critical for sterilization, flavor extraction, and the removal of unwanted volatile compounds.

It is important to note that the exact numbers provided, such as temperature and quantities, are references and may vary depending on specific requirements.

In the baseline solution, thermal energy is provided by a natural gas steam generator.

Table 1. Heating process in the brewery test case.

Phase	Fluid	Mass	Thermal process
Water heating	Water	1400 kg	From 10°C to 80°C
Mashing	Mash	600 kg	From 60°C to 80°C, 1 K min ⁻¹
Pre-Boiling	Wort	600 kg	From 80°C to 100°C
Boiling	Wort	600 kg	Evaporation of 10% in mass in 75 mins

4.2 HTHP implementation

A sketch of the HTHP for the considered test cases is presented in Fig. 5. Two scenarios have been considered. In the first the HTHP is implemented in the actual process, as presented in Table 1. The water heating is performed in a counter-flow heat exchanger (Hx_1), the mashing and the following process are performed in a second tank, assuming the heat exchange is realized between CO_2 and Mash (or Wort) at constant temperature using a second heat exchanger (Hx_2). Valves V_1 and V_2 are used to switch between the heat exchanger Hx_1 and Hx_2 . As the CO_2 cycle in this simple configuration cannot operate efficiently against constant temperature profile higher than 80°C, in this scenario electrical heating is used for Pre-Boiling and Boiling.

In the second scenario a modification of the process is hypothesized to take full advantage of the HTHP. As not all the heated water is used in the early stage of production (on the opposite, it is mainly used for cleaning after the production cycle), in this second scenario the water heating process is performed at two different times. First the 450 kg of water necessary to obtain the 600 kg of mash are heated using Hx_1 . Then, the mashing process is

performed as in the previous case using the Hx₂. The heating of the remaining 950 kg of water is then performed contemporary to the Pre-Boiling using Hx₂ and Hx₁ in series. This allows HTHP to perform up to 100°C with satisfactory COP while complying with the prescribed limits ($p_2 < 150$ bar, $T_2 < 150$ °C), and reduce the use of the electrical heating to the boiling stage.

Fig. 5. The HTHP applied to the Brewery test case: a) system schematic and main components; b) thermodynamic cycle example when Hx₂ and Hx₁ are used in series.

Once the process design conditions are identified, the optimal working point for the HTHP has been computed for each process and for different source temperature, according to the computational scheme presented before. To consider the impact of the different ambient temperatures during the year, Strasburg yearly temperature profile has been used. The yearly unit performance has been obtained as a weighted average using the frequency of each ambient temperature as a weighting function.

4.3 Case Study Results

The optimal COP for the different processes and scenarios is reported in Table 2.

From Table 2, we notice two different scenarios with distinct approaches for all stages, with either the same or better COP in all stages for Scenario 2. The COP is overall higher in Scenario 2, resulting in good energy savings. Additionally, when comparing Scenario 1 of HTHP with the baseline, we observe a higher COP and significant energy savings.

Table 2. HTHP performance compared to the baseline solution.

Actual Process	Baseline	Scenario 1		New Process	Scenario 2	
	Energy [MJ]	Energy [MJ]	COP		Energy [MJ]	COP
Water heating (1400 kg)	432.2	82.4	4.98	Water heating (450 kg)	26.5	4.98
Mashing	45.5	29.0	1.5	Mashing	29.0	1.5
Pre-Boiling	51.8	49.2	1 §	Water heating (950 kg) & Pre-Boiling	74.5	4.40
Boiling	142.1	135	1 §	Boiling	135	1 §
TOTAL/Average	671.6	295.5	2.16		265.0	2.40

§ = Electrical Heater

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the optimization of HTHPs using CO₂ as a refrigerant in a transcritical cycle was addressed. A detailed thermodynamic analysis of the system was conducted, focusing on identifying the optimal operating conditions to maximize COP. The methodology employed incorporated a pinch-point analysis and optimization framework, enabling the exploration of design spaces under various boundary conditions. The results demonstrated the significant influence of the pinch point analysis and operation conditions on the cycle's performance.

For the brewery case study, the proposed HTHP system achieved notable energy savings and higher efficiency compared to conventional natural gas systems.

6 FUTURE WORK

Future research will focus on improving performance through a detailed analysis of specific power consumption and volumetric heat capacity. In addition, advanced control strategies can be applied to optimize off-design operations and ensure reliable performance under variable conditions. Real-time optimization methods, such as Extremum Seeking Control (ESC), may also be explored. Furthermore, improving thermal recovery techniques could further reduce energy consumption and enhance the system's efficiency.

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NOMENCLATURE

T	Temperature, °C	<i>Subscripts</i>
h	Enthalpy, kJ/kg	ihx Internal heat exchanger
p	Pressure, bar	is Isentropic
		pp Pinch point
<i>Acronyms</i>		pi Process inlet
HTHP	High Temperature Heat Pump	po Process outlet
IHX	Internal Heat Exchanger	s Source
COP	Coefficient of Performance	
HPV	High Pressure Valve	

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